

Business applications of Artificial Intelligence

Agriculture, forestry, and
fishing sector briefing paper

Innovate
UK

BridgeAI

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About the briefing paper series

A significant barrier to AI adoption in the business world is the scarcity of clear, accessible information on how to leverage AI to enhance organisational productivity. Understanding the practical applications of AI is a prerequisite for companies to identify relevant opportunities and develop a strategy to operationalise them. To address this need, the AI Governance and Regulatory Innovation team at The Alan Turing Institute is pursuing a research project to illuminate how businesses in the four BridgeAI priority sectors of agriculture, forestry and fishing, construction, creative industries, and transportation and storage can leverage AI to be more productive.

The first milestone of this project is the publication of a framework for categorising and analysing business applications of AI and a brief analysis of sector-specific AI use cases. Our findings are published as a **series of five documents**: four sector-specific briefings complemented by a paper presenting a framework to categorise and analyse AI use cases. The sector briefings offer a short analysis of the high-level economic features of each

sector in the UK, the specific challenges to AI adoption faced by businesses in that sector, and five business applications of AI per sector. Each sector brief can be read as a standalone document. The paper on the classification framework presents the tool that we developed to categorise and analyse AI use cases in a business context. In addition to providing the hermeneutical structure underpinning our research, this tool provides a valuable resource for businesses trying to identify relevant AI opportunities. Companies can use this framework as a starting point to build on and develop their bespoke methodology to identify, select, and implement the right AI solutions.

The second milestone of this project will be to refine the framework based on feedback collected after the publication of this first exploratory version and expand its scope to include information about the risks connected to each AI use case and the mitigation strategies that can be adopted to address those risks in that specific context.

Desired impact

Our research aims to support businesses at the early stages of their AI adoption cycle. By providing a conceptual framework to systematically categorise business applications of AI and offering concrete examples of sector-specific AI applications, we hope to help businesses identify possible uses of AI in their area, understand the nature of relevant technological solutions, and develop a sound strategy to operationalise those solutions responsibly.

Intended audience

The audience for this briefing series is primarily businesses within the BridgeAI priority sectors looking to adopt AI to support their operations. It is worth noting that the accompanying framework was developed based on generalised principles which are applicable to any sector and should, therefore, provide value to a wider audience, including non-commercial organisations. In addition to benefiting companies, this briefing series provides valuable resources for government officials and regulators aiming to understand how businesses use AI, as well as for training officers and advisors seeking a systematic approach to developing AI strategies for business.

AI Governance and Regulatory Innovation team

This work has been completed by researchers from The Alan Turing Institute who are part of the AI Governance and Regulatory Innovation team based within the Public Policy programme. As part of our offering for the BridgeAI programme, we support UK businesses navigate the increasingly complex AI governance landscape. This is delivered through training and sector-specific research on some of the most pressing AI governance issues, as well as by engaging with regional AI policy stakeholders to help consolidate a nationwide community of actors invested in responsible AI governance.

Introduction

Artificial intelligence (AI) is rapidly transforming the global economy, yet many sectors of the business world are only beginning to explore the opportunities AI technologies offer. Despite AI adoption being on the rise globally, the technology's potential to support organisations by improving their productivity and competitiveness remains partially unexplored in many economic areas. For instance, only 20% of small companies in the UK say they use at least one AI tool as part of their operations, despite 55% stating that AI could provide benefits to their business.¹ To ensure AI will benefit a wide range of sectors and regions and support businesses in their AI adoption journey, the UK government launched several high-impact initiatives to “invest and plan for the long-term needs of the [country's] AI ecosystem”.² These include, among others, the BridgeAI programme, which aims to foster the development and adoption of AI technologies in sectors with high potential for AI-driven economic transformation.³

Despite important steps forward, several barriers to widespread AI adoption still exist. These include the high cost of AI solutions, the uncertainty of their return on investment,⁴ the scarcity of relevant technical and business skills in the labour market,⁵ regulatory uncertainty

related to the development and use of AI,⁶ low rates of senior management buy-in, the difficulty of collecting or accessing high-quality data,⁷ and scepticism for some AI applications caused by ethical concerns around issues such as bias and privacy. At a more fundamental level, many companies struggle to identify the right AI opportunities due to a general lack of awareness about the full range of practical business applications of these technologies. In other words, many companies are unsure about how exactly to leverage the potential of AI to support their business goals. For instance, a recent survey of 100 business leaders from different countries and sectors found that while “leaders are overwhelmingly looking at AI as an opportunity, the picture is not yet clear on how to harness this opportunity practically.”⁸

One way to address this uncertainty is disseminating knowledge about existing AI use cases and best practices in the industry. Understanding how other companies use AI technologies, be it to support internal functions or to build better products and services, enables businesses that are considering embarking on the journey of AI adoption to think creatively about how AI can add value to their organisation.

1 Russell, C. & E. Quist (2024). *Redefining intelligence: The growth of AI among small businesses*. Federation of Small Businesses. <https://www.fsb.org.uk/resource-report/redefining-intelligence.html>.

2 UK Government (2021). *National AI Strategy*. <https://www.gov.uk/government/publications/national-ai-strategy/national-ai-strategy-html-version>.

3 Innovate UK (2023). *BridgeAI*. <https://iuk.ktn-uk.org/programme/bridgeai/>.

4 CDEI (2021). *UK Business Innovation Survey*. https://assets.publishing.service.gov.uk/media/61bb2e77e90e07044462d8b7/Business_Innovation_Survey_2021.pdf.

5 *AI ecosystem survey informing the National AI Strategy*. The Alan Turing Institute, https://www.turing.ac.uk/sites/default/files/2021-09/ai-strategy-survey_results_020921.pdf.

6 Gillespie, N., S. Lockey, C. Curtis, et al. (2023). *Trust in Artificial Intelligence: A global study*. The University of Queensland and KPMG Australia. https://policy-futures.centre.uq.edu.au/files/16650/Trust%20in%20AI%20Global%20Report_2023_UQ.pdf.

7 Mittal, N., Saif, I. & Ammanath, B. (2022). *Fueling the AI transformation: Four key actions powering widespread value from AI, right now*. Deloitte, <https://www2.deloitte.com/content/dam/Deloitte/us/Documents/deloitte-analytics/us-ai-institute-state-of-ai-fifth-edition.pdf>.

8 Bicakci, B. et al. (2024). *Leadership in the Age of AI*. EgonZehnder and Kearney. <https://www.egonzehnder.com/leadership-in-the-age-of-ai>.

Building on this premise, this briefing aims to contribute to demystifying how businesses in the agriculture, forestry, and fishing sector can use AI to be more competitive, sustainable, and productive. The first part of the briefing offers an overview of the key economic features of the UK's agriculture, forestry, and fishing sector, including a brief discussion of sector-specific challenges to AI adoption. In the second part, we leverage the **AI use case classification framework** to discuss five sectoral AI applications. Each AI use case is accompanied by a use case card, which provides a visual summary of the key information related to that application. These examples illustrate the wide-ranging and diverse potential applications of AI in the agriculture, forestry, and fishing sector.

Sector overview and challenges to AI adoption

Agriculture, forestry, and fishing is the sector that grows fruits, vegetables and flowers, raises animals for meat, dairy or eggs, farms and catches fish, and manages forests to produce timber and pulp. The sector is the essential supplier underpinning the food and beverage sector, providing half of the consumed food and the guardianship of enormous quantities of the natural environment. Around 71% of the UK's land use is attributed to roughly 217,000 farm holdings of various sizes for activities ranging from producing crops and cultivating vegetables to rearing livestock and rough grazing.⁹ In 2022, the sector contributed 0.56% of the UK's total GDP (£11.5 billion)¹⁰ and employed approximately 1% of the country's workforce.¹¹

The sector faces challenges that are impacting its growth. Two major issues are the relatively low average earnings of specialised workers¹² and a progressively ageing workforce. The sector is especially burdened by shortages of seasonal and non-seasonal labour necessary to cultivate and harvest crops or drive heavy goods vehicles.¹³

Finally, the sector can be negatively impacted by phenomena related to climate change, including unpredictable weather patterns, droughts, and extreme weather events, which can significantly affect production.

These challenges, coupled with relatively low technology adoption suggest that there could be a role for AI systems in supporting productivity growth in agriculture, forestry, and fishing.

In fact, AI could support processes across the entire value chain, from resource management and production to quality control, procurement, and sales. Despite the potential benefits of AI, however, the uptake of AI technologies has been slow compared to other industries. Factors such as the cost of investment in AI, the lack of bespoke AI and data skills and training¹⁴, and a general lack of clarity about how AI can be used in practice to address the needs of the sector have contributed to its low AI maturity¹⁵.

9 Department for Environment, Food & Rural Affairs. (2022). *Agriculture in the UK Dashboard*. <https://defra-farming-stats.github.io/auk-dashboard/#land-use>.

10 Office for National Statistics (2024). *Regional gross value added (balanced) by industry; all ITL regions*. <https://www.ons.gov.uk/economy/grossvalueaddedgva/datasets/nominalandrealregionalgrossvalueaddedbalancedbyindustry>.

11 Department for Environment, Food & Rural Affairs. (2022). *Agriculture in the UK Evidence Pack*. https://assets.publishing.service.gov.uk/media/6331b071e90e0711d5d595df/AUK_Evidence_Pack_2021_Sept22.pdf.

12 It is estimated that the average salary in the sector is £16 per hour compared to national average of £38 per hour (source: Department for Environment, Food & Rural Affairs. (2022). *Agriculture in the UK Evidence Pack*. https://assets.publishing.service.gov.uk/media/6331b071e90e0711d5d595df/AUK_Evidence_Pack_2021_Sept22.pdf).

13 UK Parliament. (2021). *Labour shortages in the food and farming sector*. <https://committees.parliament.uk/work/1497/labour-shortages-in-the-food-and-farming-sector/>.

14 Barclays (2021) *Insight to AI in UK Agritech* https://www.barclays.co.uk/content/dam/documents/business/business-insight/Insights_AI_in_Agriculture.pdf.

15 InnovateUK (2023) *Accelerating Agritech adoption in the UK* <https://iuk.ktn-uk.org/news/accelerating-agritech-adoption-in-the-uk/#:~:text=The%20Agriculture%20sector%20is%20often,this%20can%20be%20worrying>.

Sector structure

The agriculture, forestry, and fishing sector encompasses a diverse range of activities. For the purposes of this research, we refer to the UK Standard Industrial Classification (SIC) sub-sector categorisation:¹³

- Crop
- Animal production and hunting
- Forestry and logging
- Fishing and aquaculture

The 'Crop' sub-sector includes businesses that grow cereals, seeds, vegetables, fruit, ornamental plants, and flowers. The 'Animal production and hunting' sub-sector comprises businesses that farm animals such as cattle, sheep, pigs, and poultry, as well as commercial hunting. The 'Forestry and logging' sub-sector includes businesses that manage and exploit forests to produce wood and pulp. The 'Fishing and aquaculture' sub-sector includes both businesses that catch fish in the sea or freshwater, and those that farm marine or freshwater plants and animals. We also consider agrochemical businesses to form part of this sector. These companies do not directly farm plants or animals but produce the various chemical products used in agriculture, including fertilisers and pesticides. We categorise them into sub-sectors based on the primary use of their products. Finally, we include in these sectors also companies providing relevant support services such as research, consulting, and specialised equipment.

¹³ Office for National Statistics (2007). *UK SIC 2007*. <https://www.ons.gov.uk/methodology/classificationsandstandards/ukstandardindustrialclassificationofeconomicactivities/uksic2007>.

AI applications for the agriculture, forestry, and fishing sector

Despite the relatively slow rate of AI adoption, businesses in the agriculture, forestry, and fishing sector are increasingly integrating AI solutions into their operations. Concrete examples include livestock monitoring, irrigation and herbicide spraying optimisation, crop yield prediction, and soil analysis through satellite images. In this section is a description of five agriculture, forestry, and fishing use cases that we analysed using the framework presented in this **accompanying paper**.

Livestock health monitoring

Alongside other solutions for more effective farming, businesses are exploring ways to improve the health of farmed animals, including more closely monitoring livestock to identify early signs of diseases. Constant monitoring of animals, however, is a resource-intensive process. AI can automate livestock monitoring, helping farmers cut costs and free up some of their time to work elsewhere. For example, an AI system can be used to analyse cattle's gait based on video footage captured by

CCTV cameras. If available, the system can also pull in ID data from sort gates or Radio Frequency Identification chips carried by the animals. Based on this data, the system can assign mobility scores to each animal and calculate an interval of predicted lameness, providing insights that enable farmers to make targeted medical interventions before the health of affected animals deteriorates further.

Business challenge:

Improve animal health and livestock productivity.

Solution:

An AI system monitors the health conditions of cattle each time they pass in front of a camera and detects when targeted medical interventions are required based on their gait.

Organisation

Type of use case

Process-centric

Business function

Management of organisational assets

Data

Type of input data

Numerical, Textual, Visual

Processing of personal data

No

AI system

AI system capabilities

Prediction and forecasting, Recognition and detection

Environment

Virtual

Readiness level

Operational

Economic sector

Sector

Agriculture

Sub-sector

Animal production and hunting

Weed detection for autonomous herbicide spraying

Weed control is a resource-intensive and environmentally impactful process for businesses in the crops industry. While removing unwanted weeds is required to ensure crops receive sufficient water, nutrients, and sunlight, traditional approaches usually entail spraying herbicides over the entire crop field, leading to wastage and unnecessary pollution. AI can be used to adopt a more targeted approach, enabling farmers to spray herbicide only

on selected spots where unwanted weeds are present. This approach could lead to cost savings, increased yields, and reduced environmental impact. For example, a machine vision system can analyse data collected by cameras mounted on herbicide sprayers dragged across the field by a tractor. This data is then processed in real-time by an AI system that detects target areas in which weeds are present based on their colour and autonomously turns individual nozzles on and off to only remove unwanted weeds.

Business challenge:

Reduce the costs and environmental impact of weed control processes.

Solution:

An AI system analyses data collected by cameras mounted on herbicide sprayers dragged across the field by a tractor. The system detects target areas where unwanted weeds are present and turns individual nozzles on and off to remove them.

Organisation

Type of use case

Process-centric

Business function

Management of organisational assets

Data

Type of input data

Visual

Processing of personal data

No

AI system

AI system capabilities

Goal-directed action, Recognition and detection

Environment

Physical

Readiness level

Operational

Economic sector

Sector

Agriculture

Sub-sector

Crop

Automated plant watering control

Water deficit poses a significant challenge in farming. Droughts can lead to lower yields and price increases, cutting farmers' profits. Possible AI solutions to improve water management are currently under development. For example, researchers have tested a plant watering control system designed to reduce water consumption while maintaining the humidity required by the plants under specific soil conditions. Similar solutions, which could be applicable to all types of crop businesses, are based on AI

models that analyse soil and environmental conditions through data collected by in-situ sensors and, taking into account the time of the day, activate the irrigation system with the goal of optimising water consumption.

Business challenge:

Optimise water consumption in irrigation systems.

Solution:

An AI system analyses soil and environmental conditions in crop fields and activates irrigation systems as necessary to optimise water consumption.

Organisation

Type of use case

Process-centric

Business function

Management of organisational assets

Data

Type of input data

Signal

Processing of personal data

No

AI system

AI system capabilities

Goal-directed action, Optimisation, Recognition and detection

Environment

Physical

Readiness level

Proof of concept

Economic sector

Sector

Agriculture

Sub-sector

Crop

Soil moisture analysis

Correctly estimating soil moisture content can help businesses assess plant health, predict crop yields, and optimise water usage. Precision agriculture has traditionally relied on sensor data to measure moisture. More recently, satellite images are complementing or replacing in-situ sensor data as more affordable options, opening new opportunities to use AI technologies for the management of land. For example, an AI system can analyse satellite images to estimate soil moisture

content in different areas of a selected portion of land. The results of this analysis provide farmers with useful information to support their land management choices, including what types of crops to plant in specific sections of the land to maximise yield, and how to optimise water usage.

Business challenge:

Reduce the costs of soil moisture analysis for land management.

Solution:

An AI system uses satellite images to estimate the soil moisture content of land, helping farmers optimise water usage and choose what types of crops to plant to maximise yield.

Organisation

Type of use case

Process-centric

Business function

Management of organisational assets

Data

Type of input data

Geospatial, Visual

Processing of personal data

No

AI system

AI system capabilities

Recognition and detection

Environment

Virtual

Readiness level

Proof of concept

Economic sector

Sector

Agriculture

Sub-sector

Crop

Bird song recognition for farmland biodiversity tracking

As older UK farm subsidy programmes are gradually replaced by Environmental Land Management schemes – which reward, among other things, the protection of the natural environment alongside food production – farms that can provide evidence of sustainable practices will be eligible for financial incentives. AI can play a crucial role in tracking and documenting farm biodiversity. For example, an AI system can be used to analyse audio

recordings of bird sounds to identify the number of species present on a specific portion of land. Bird biodiversity is a valuable indicator of the diversity of insects and seeds above ground, as well as the richness of life in the soil. Unlike manual biodiversity tracking, similar AI solutions offer the advantage of continuous, around-the-clock analysis and can even detect sounds that are inaudible to the human ear.

Business challenge:

Around-the-clock tracking and documentation of farmland biodiversity.

Solution:

An AI system analyses bird song to identify the bird biodiversity of a an area of land. Bird biodiversity is an indicator of the diversity of insects and seeds above ground, as well as the richness of life in the soil.

Organisation

Type of use case

Process-centric

Business function

Management of organisational assets

Data

Type of input data

Audio

Processing of personal data

No

AI system

AI system capabilities

Recognition and detection

Environment

Virtual

Readiness level

Operational

Economic sector

Sector

Agriculture

Sub-sector

Crop

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